

EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND TEACHING-LEARNING OPPORTUNITIES IN SUSTAINING ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the effect of emergency management practices and teaching-learning opportunities in sustaining organizational effectiveness. Furthermore, this attempted to determine if there is a significant relationship between organizational effectiveness and that of emergency management and teaching-learning opportunities. Using a descriptive correlational study method, it involved 110 public elementary school teachers from 10 schools in the Ambray District, during the academic year 2020-2021. Self-made questionnaire was employed to measure the data about the organizational effectiveness of Ambray District in terms of learner's motivation, teaching process and performance of schools and teachers which undergone internal and external validation through the help of the panel of examiners and group of teachers. Results revealed that there is significant relationship between the organizational effectiveness and that of emergency management and teaching-learning opportunities. However, it is clear to note based on the given results that organizational effectiveness has a significant correlation to management practices and the teaching-learning process. Organizational effectiveness can truly be determined by the kind of management exhibited by the school heads.

Keywords: emergency management, teaching-learning opportunities and organizational effectiveness